

Synthesis of Lanthanide(III) Complexes of Naphthylacetic Acids

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In our previous papers^{1,2}, the behaviour of complexes of aryloxyacetic acids has been described wherein the important role played by the ether oxygen in aryloxyacetic acids has been realised. However, in arylacetic acids such ether oxygens are absent. The present work was undertaken with a view to compare the formation and properties of hitherto unknown lanthanide complexes of naphthylacetic acids with that of naphthoxyacetic acids, and in what way the absence of ether oxygen affects the coordinating capabilities of these naphthylacetic acids. It would be appropriate to mention here that the formation and properties of lanthanide(III) complexes of phenylacetic acid have already been described³. It has been shown that the phenylacetic acid forms complexes of the type $\text{Ln}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{COO})_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ³⁻⁵ in which the ligand acts as a bidentate chelate. A few lanthanide(III) complexes of 1-naphthylacetic acid with the general formula $\text{Ln}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{CH}_2\text{COO})_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are also known ($\text{Ln} = \text{Ce}, \text{Pr}, \text{Nd}, \text{Sm}$ and Eu)^{5,6}. In these cases also the naphthylacetic acid behaves as a bidentate ligand. However, perusal of literature reveals that lanthanide(III) complexes with 2-naphthylacetic acid are hitherto unknown. Hence it would be of interest to synthesise the complexes of 2-naphthylacetic acid with lanthanide ions and compare the same with those of the other arylacetic acids, apart from those of naphthoxyacetic acids. With this view Ln(III) complexes of 2-naphthylacetic acid ($\text{Ln(III)} = \text{La}, \text{Pr}, \text{Nd}, \text{Sm}, \text{Gd}, \text{Tb}$ and Dy) and Ln(III) complexes with 1-naphthylacetic acid ($\text{Ln(III)} = \text{La}, \text{Gd}, \text{Tb}$ and Dy) were prepared. The known Ln(III) complexes with phenylacetic acid and 1-naphthylacetic acid were also prepared for the sake of comparative study.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are amorphous and insoluble in water. They are soluble in DMF and are non-conducting as shown by their molar conductance values ($2-5 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$).

All the complexes begin to lose water at about 80° and the weight-loss measured at 95° corresponds to the lattice-held water (2 water molecules). Isothermal heating at 120° and above does not indicate any further loss of water and this may indicate the absence of coordinated water molecules in the complexes.

Two lanthanum(III) complexes are diamagnetic. Other lanthanide(III) complexes are paramagnetic and the μ_{eff} values are closer to their respective theoretical values, except for Sm^{III} (Table 1). The magnetic moments of the Sm^{III} complexes do deviate from the theoretical value for

reasons already known⁷.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd.**	Metal% : Found/(Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.
[La(TNPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	18.95 (19.03)	Dia.
[Pr(TNPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	18.82 (19.25)	3.62
[Nd(TNPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	19.12 (19.62)	3.65
[Sm(TNPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	20.20 (20.28)	1.54
[Gd(TNPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	20.95 (21.01)	8.06
[Tb(TNPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	20.76 (21.19)	9.51
[Dy(TNPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	20.81 (21.56)	10.65
[La(NPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	19.21 (19.03)	Dia
[Gd(NPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	20.64 (21.01)	7.88
[Tb(NPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	20.92 (21.19)	9.64
[Dy(NPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	21.74 (21.56)	10.43

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

**NPLAH = 1-naphthylacetic acid, TNPLAH = 2-naphthylacetic acid.

The sodium salt of 2-naphthylacetic acid reveals $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ bands at 1 565 and 1 385 cm^{-1} respectively. The $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ bands of La^{III} , Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} , Sm^{III} , Gd^{III} , Tb^{III} and Dy^{III} complexes occur respectively at 1 532, 1 530, 1 527, 1 530, 1 530, 1 530 and 1 530 cm^{-1} and those for $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ at 1 405, 1 405, 1 405, 1 407, 1 410, 1 405 and 1 407 cm^{-1} . The $\Delta\nu$ values for the complexes lie in the range 120–127 cm^{-1} and for the sodium salt it is 180 cm^{-1} . This suggests bidentate chelate mode of carboxylate coordination in all these complexes².

The sodium salt of 1-naphthylacetic acid exhibits $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ band at 1 547 cm^{-1} and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ at 1 373 cm^{-1} . The La^{III} , Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} , Sm^{III} , Gd^{III} , Tb^{III} and Dy^{III} complexes of 1-naphthylacetic acid show $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ bands at 1 530, 1 528, 1 534, 1 530, 1 532, 1 532 and 1 533 cm^{-1} and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ bands at 1 383, 1 382, 1 385, 1 380, 1 385, 1 385 and 1 386 cm^{-1} respectively. These values suggest biden-

tate chelate mode of coordination in all these complexes. All the complexes of 1- and 2-naphthylacetic acids exhibit a broad band at 3 400 and 3 500 cm^{-1} respectively, indicating the presence of water molecules in the complexes.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF Ln(III) COMPLEXES*

Compd.**	ν_{max} cm^{-1}	Nephelau. ratio β	Sinha parameter s(%)	Bonding parameter $b^{1/2}$
[Pr(PLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	21 186 ^a	0.993 7	0.634 0	0.056 1
[Pr(NPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	21 186 ^a	0.993 7	0.634 0	0.056 1
[Pr(TNPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	21 186 ^a	0.993 7	0.634 0	0.056 1
[Pr(ONAP) ₃].2H ₂ O	21 186 ^a	0.993 7	0.634 0	0.056 1
[Pr(TNAP) ₃].2H ₂ O	21 195 ^a	0.994 1	0.593 5	0.054 3
[Nd(PLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	17 053 ^b	0.985 7	1.450 7	0.084 6
[Nd(NPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	17 053 ^b	0.985 7	1.450 7	0.084 6
[Nd(TNPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	17 053 ^b	0.985 7	1.450 7	0.084 6
[Nd(ONAP) ₃].2H ₂ O	17 053 ^b	0.985 7	1.450 7	0.084 6
[Nd(TNAP) ₃].2H ₂ O	17 059 ^b	0.986 0	1.419 8	0.083 6
[Sm(PLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	24 272 ^c	0.975 7	2.490 5	0.110 2
[Sm(NPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	24 272 ^c	0.975 7	2.490 5	0.110 2
[Sm(TNPLA) ₃].2H ₂ O	24 272 ^c	0.975 7	2.490 5	0.110 2
[Sm(ONAP) ₃].2H ₂ O	24 272 ^c	0.975 7	2.490 5	0.110 2
[Sm(TNAP) ₃].2H ₂ O	24 284 ^c	0.976 2	2.438 0	0.109 1

* Values for aryloxyacetato complexes are taken from ref. 2.

** PLA_H = phenylacetic acid, ONAPH = 1-naphthoxyacetic acid, TNAPH = 2-naphthoxyacetic acid.

The electronic spectral data (Table 1) reveal that the electron density of the carboxylate group is nearly the same in the complexes of arylacetic acids as reflected by $b^{1/2}$ values. This indicates that only the inductive effect operates in these systems. It could also be seen that in the complexes of aryloxyacetic acids the electron density of the carboxylate group is affected by both mesomeric and inductive effects as revealed by their $b^{1/2}$ values.

As the size of the cation is decreased, an increased M-L covalency is expected for Ln(III) cations. The $b^{1/2}$ values for tris(2-naphthylacetato)praseodymium(III)dihydrate, tris(2-naphthylacetato)neodymium(III)dihydrate and tris(2-naphthylacetato)samarium(III)dihydrate are 0.0561, 0.0846 and 0.1102 respectively, indicating the M-L covalency order : Sm^{III} > Nd^{III} > Pr^{III}.

From the above studies, the composition of the rare earth complexes can be represented as [M(RCOO)₃].2H₂O with a coordination number of six for the metal ion. A coordination number 6 is reflected in the hypersensitive transition of Nd^{III} chelates and in the thermal studies of all these chelates. The $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ values of all the complexes indicate the bidentate chelate mode of carboxylate coordination. The non-ionic nature of the complexes is revealed by the lower molar conductance values in DMF. The formula is supported by elemental analysis for all the complexes studied.

Experimental

Rare earth oxides (99.9% purity), were obtained from Indian Rare Earths Ltd., Trivandrum. Lanthanide chlorides were prepared by dissolving the calculated amount of oxide in concentrated hydrochloric acid and then evaporating to get the residue. The residue was dissolved in water and the chloride solution was used for the preparation of complexes. The ligands 1- and 2-naphthylacetic acids (Sigma) were used as such.

The newer complexes of the 1-naphthylacetic acid reported herein were prepared as follows. To a solution of 1-naphthylacetic acid (1.86 g, 0.01 mol) in aqueous acetone (1 : 2, 150 ml), drops of aqueous ammonia (1 : 6) were added to bring the pH to 6.5–7. It was then treated with a solution of lanthanide(III) chloride (0.0033 mol) in aqueous acetone (1 : 2, 50 ml). The resulting complex was washed with aqueous acetone (1 : 2), dried in air and then under reduced pressure over anhydrous calcium chloride.

The lanthanide(III) chelates of 2-naphthylacetic acid were prepared as follows. To a solution of 2-naphthylacetic acid (1.86 g, 0.01 mol) in aqueous ethanol (1 : 1, 300 ml), drops of aqueous ammonia (1 : 6) were added to bring the pH to 6.5–7. It was then treated with a solution of lanthanide(III) chloride (0.0033 mol) in aqueous ethanol (1 : 1, 50 ml). The resulting complex was washed with aqueous ethanol (1 : 1), dried in air and then under reduced pressure over anhydrous calcium chloride.

The metal content of the complexes was estimated by incinerating them to the oxides. Conductivity was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity meter with a dip-type cell fitted with a platinised platinum electrode (cell constant, 0.734), using approximately 1×10^{-3} M solution of the complexes. Magnetic susceptibility was measured using solid samples on a Gouy type magnetic balance at room temperature (303–308 K). Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 527 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (nujol) on a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer.

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